

Chemistry of Vanadium. Part VI*. Studies on the Formation of Vanadyl (VO)³⁺ Salts of Organic Acids

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Vanadyl (VO)²⁺ salts of several organic acids have been prepared by the action of VOCl₃ on molten acids. Properties of the products have been studied and structures discussed.

Hypovanadic acid unites with many organic acids to form stable and in most cases crystalline compounds (Gain, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1908, viii, 14, 224; Berzelius, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1831, 22, 1). Fischer (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1916, 30, 190) observed that vanadium pentoxide dissolved in organic and inorganic acids to form vanadyl salts. Vanadium oxytrichloride is known to form substitution products with many organic compounds. Funk *et al.* (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1958, 296, 36) reported the formation of VO(o-ClC₆H₄O)₃, VO(p-ClC₆H₄O)₃, and VO(OPh)₃ with *ortho*- and *para*-chlorophenols and phenol respectively and of VOCl₂(C₆H₇O₂), VOCl(C₆H₇O₂)₂, and VO(C₆H₇O₂)₂ with methyl malonate under different conditions. They also prepared trialkyl esters of the types VO(OMe)₃ and VO(OEt)₃.

A careful review of the literature shows that practically no systematic work has been done on the formation of vanadyl (VO)³⁺ derivatives of organic acids. The present work was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of these compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadium oxytrichloride was prepared by the method of Roscoe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1868, 21, 342) and purified by distillation. It was redistilled over metallic sodium; the pure compound was extracted with anhydrous CCl₄ and analysed for purity. Analysis confirmed the purity of the product. (Found: V, 29.28; Cl, 61.54. Calc. for VOCl₃: V, 29.39; Cl, 61.38%). Other chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E. Merck's 'extra pure' quality. The acids were recrystallised before use.

General Method of Preparation.—An excess of the acid suspension in CCl₄ was added to a solution of VOCl₃ in CCl₄ and mixed well in a reaction vessel connected to CaCl₂ and P₂O₅ tubes. The mixture was heated on an oil bath gently in the beginning and then at a temperature 10-15° higher than the melting point of the acid. When the evolution of HCl gas had ceased, the heated mass was cooled and washed with anhydrous ether till free of the acid. It was dried and analysed.

Vanadium was estimated in H₂SO₄ (dil.) by reduction with SO₂, removal of SO₂ by CO₂, and titration with a standard KMnO₄ solution at 70°. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated in a few cases by combustion method.

General Properties.—In all the cases crystalline, coloured, slightly hygroscopic but fairly stable compounds were obtained. These compounds are soluble in ethanol, acetone, or ethyl acetate and insoluble in ether, benzene, CCl₄, or CHCl₃. These are slowly hydrolysed by cold water or dilute mineral acids and readily when boiled, and are fairly soluble in alkali solutions. The compounds did not respond to tests for chlorine.

One molecule of VOCl₃ reacts with three molecules of monobasic acids and two molecules of dibasic acids with formation of the corresponding salts. With dibasic acids the reaction is more vigorous and is completed in comparatively small time.

* Part V: *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 543.

In the case of citric acid, only one molecule of VOCl_3 reacts with one molecule of the acid and $(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{C}(\text{OH})(\text{COO})_3(\text{VO})$ is formed, showing that hydrogen of only carboxylic groups is being displaced.

TABLE I

Vanadyl (VO)³⁺ salts of organic acids.

No.	Acids.	Colour.	M.P.	%Vanadium.		%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		Probable formula.
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
1	Lauric	Greyish brown	61°	7.60	7.68	64.21	65.06	10.15	10.38	$[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{COO}]_3(\text{VO})$
2	Myristic	Greyish black	37°	6.76	6.82	$[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{12}\text{COO}]_3(\text{VO})$
3	Palmitic	Blackish brown	42°	6.09	6.13	$[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{14}\text{COO}]_3(\text{VO})$
4	Stearic	Greenish black	50°	5.63	5.57	68.93	70.74	11.18	11.47	$[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}]_3(\text{VO})$
5	Oleic	Light brown	37°	5.67	5.60	62.02	71.22	10.57	10.88	$[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{CH}=\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{COO}]_3(\text{VO})$
6	Benzoic	Bright yellow	167°	11.69	11.86	57.88	58.60	3.53	3.49	$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_3(\text{VO})$
7	<i>o</i> -Toluic	Dirty yellow	183°	10.70	10.81	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)\text{COO}]_3(\text{VO})$
8	Sebacic	Yellowish brown	56°	13.95	13.89	$[(\text{CH}_2)_8(\text{COO})_2]_3(\text{VO})_2$
9	Succinic	Greyish brown	135°	21.30	21.16	$[(\text{CH}_2)_4(\text{COO})_2]_3(\text{VO})_2$
10	Phthalic	Yellowish green	213°	16.20	16.29	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{COO})_2]_3(\text{VO})_2$
11	Citric	Greenish black	163°	20.23	20.15	28.72	28.13	1.89	1.96	$(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{C}(\text{OH})(\text{COO})_3(\text{VO})$

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing facilities.

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Received October 11, 1960.